

Effect of Perceived Stress and Self-Efficacy on Academic Procrastination among College Students

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Abstract:- This study is done to assess the relationship between Perceived Stress, Self-Efficacy and Academic Procrastination among college students and to examine the influence of academic procrastination on Perceived Stress and Self-Efficacy among college students. The main rationale for conducting this research is to understand Effect of Perceived Stress and Self-Efficacy on Academic Procrastination and Among College Students. The data was collected by 70 participants aged between 19-23 years currently pursuing Under graduation and Post-graduation. The scales used for the study were The Perceived Stress Scale by (Cohen et al., 1983), The General Self-Efficacy Scale by Schwarzer, R., & Jerusalem M. (1995) and General Procrastination Scale by (Lay, 1986). The results showed that there is a significant relationship between Perceived Stress, Self-Efficacy and Academic Procrastination among college students and there is no significant influence of Academic Procrastination on Perceived Stress and Self-Efficacy among college students.

Keywords:- Perceived Stress, Self-Efficacy, Academic Procrastination.

I. INTRODUCTION

Students experience a range of difficulties in the educational and academic sector, as well as problems in the personal-social field, throughout their academic careers. Academic procrastination is one of the most common issues in this field. Academic procrastination, in particular, involves the delay and postponement of academic activities. The procrastinator knows what he wants to do and is eager to complete the duties he has set for himself, but he has put it off. Procrastination has both internal and external consequences. Tension, regret, and self-blame are examples of internal negative effects. External negative consequences include delayed career and academic success, missed chances, and strained relationships. Academic procrastination compromises students' academic enthusiasm and progress. Students delay due to a lack of enthusiasm, low self-esteem, difficulties understanding, low energy levels, and poor organisational abilities. (Gunn, 2019). Tasks are frequently delayed by students because they are unable to see their relevance or significance, because they lack understanding of the subject, or because they are simply unsure of where to start.

The belief that one can complete a task successfully is known as self-efficacy. Therefore, if a task is thought to be simple, it will likely be attempted; otherwise, it will be avoided. In terms of feelings, self-efficacy has a low correlation with helplessness, anxiety, depression, and stress. Individual with low self-efficacy have very low self-esteem and tend to be pessimistic about their accomplishments and personal development. The sense of efficacy that facilitates a person's cognitive process is strongly related to the quality of academic achievement and decision-making. Furthermore, those with a higher sense of self-efficacy are more likely to persevere with difficult tasks.

Academic self-efficacy is a variable related to a student's ability to complete academic tasks successfully and achieve their goals perfectly (Mehmet et al., 2014). It has been discovered that one of the stress-coping approaches, active planning, explains academic procrastination on both a negative and meaningful level, whereas biochemical avoidance strategies explain it on both a positive and meaningful level. The relational screening methodology is employed in the research, which includes 374 students from Kırkkale University's Education Faculty in Turkey. In the study, the "Aitken Academic Procrastination Scale," "Academic Self-Efficacy Scale," "Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale," and "Coping with Stress Scale" are used. Path analysis modelling is used in the study to evaluate hypothesis models. The results of a model demonstrate that academic procrastination in students is described by academic self-efficacy, self-esteem, and stress-coping techniques. One research was examining the connection between academic procrastination and self-efficacy among King Saud University students. It also tries to determine whether the level of academic procrastination varies depending on variables such as college type, academic level, or students' achievement level. (Alqudah et al., 2014) The largest percentage of the sample on the procrastination academic scale was 83.6%, followed by 9.7% and 6.7%. There were no statistically significant changes based on college or academic achievement. (Malkoç & Mutlu, 2018) There is link between academic self-efficacy, academic motivation, and academic procrastination. The researchers also investigated whether academic motivation influences the association between self-efficacy and academic procrastination. The study's findings suggest that academic motivation helps to mediate the association between academic self-efficacy and academic procrastination.

It was found that Academic procrastination has no substantial association with academic accomplishment. there is a connection between academic procrastination, academic self-efficacy, and educational success. The findings indicate a negative and significant association between academic self-efficacy and academic procrastination, as well as a positive and substantial relationship between academic self-efficacy and academic accomplishment. (Yiğit et al., 2020)

The author did this research to understand the effect of Perceived Stress and Self-Efficacy on Academic Procrastination among college students.

➤ *Research Question*

1. Is there a relationship between Perceived Stress, Self-Efficacy and Academic Procrastination among College Students?
2. How does Perceived Stress, Self-Efficacy influence Academic Procrastination Among College Students?

➤ *Objectives*

1. To assess the relationship between relationship between Perceived Stress, Self-Efficacy and Academic Procrastination among college students.
2. To examine the influence of academic procrastination on Perceived Stress and Self-Efficacy among college students.

➤ *Hypotheses*

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between Perceived Stress, Self-Efficacy and Academic Procrastination among college students.

H₀₂: There is no significant influence of academic procrastination on Perceived Stress and Self-Efficacy among college students.

➤ *Sample*

The study used online survey method for data collection to study the Effect of Perceived Stress and Self-Efficacy on Academic Procrastination among college students. The sample consisted of 70 participants aged between 19-23 years pursuing Undergraduate and Postgraduate. Data was collected from males and females among students from all steams Arts, Commerce and Science studying in Bangalore Karnataka, and Jaipur Rajasthan. The data was collected using convenient sampling technique.

➤ *Variables:*

The variables that will be measured in this study are:

1. Perceived Stress
2. Academic Procrastination
3. Self-Efficacy

➤ *Operational Definitions*

Perceived Stress: The degree to which events in a person's life are viewed as stressful, unexpected, and uncontrollable is referred to as perceived stress.

Self-efficacy: Self-efficacy is an individual's belief in his or her ability to carry out the actions required to achieve specified performance goals.

Academic Procrastination: Procrastination etymologically means delaying something until tomorrow, which is usually less defined.

➤ *Procedure*

For this study, The Perceived Stress Scale, The General Self-Efficacy Scale (GSE) and General Procrastination Scale was used to collect the data, in the form of questionnaire and was shared with participants in google form. Participants were instructed on how to answer the questions and basic demographic details were collected. The participants have taken minimum of 10 minutes to answer the questions. After the data was collected, data was analysed with the help of Correlation test, Regression and the outcome was discussed.

➤ *Tools used*

- **The Perceived Stress Scale-** This scale is a reliable and widely used tool for measuring the perception of stress. It was developed by Cohen, 1983 (PSS; Cohen et al., 1983). It consists of 10-item instrument measuring the perception of stress. Reliability: Cronbach alpha= .78
- **The General Self-Efficacy Scale (GSE)** developed by Schwarzer, R., & Jerusalem, M. (1995). It is a ten-item self-report survey with four-choice responses: not at all true, barely true, moderately true, and exactly true, going from negative to positive. Internal reliability for GSE = Cronbach's alphas between .76 and .90
- **General Procrastination Scale:** Procrastination is assessed as a unidimensional and the scale was developed by (Lay, 1986). It is a 20-item scale that assesses global, trait-like procrastination tendencies across a range of tasks (e.g., "In preparing for some deadlines, I frequently waste time by doing other things.") On a 5-point scale, participants rated their level of agreement with each item. The GPS is a unidimensional scale with ten reverse-scored items that was originally validated across three studies, one of which included a community adult sample and the scale is one-factor only scale, with Cronbach alpha of 0,82 (Lay, 1986) and a retest reliability of 0,80 (Ferrari, 1989).

II. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The results were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. IBM SPSS-25 was used for data analysis. Among descriptive statistics, mean and standard deviation were used; among the inferential statistics Regression and Spearman correlation method was used to test the hypothesis.

III. RESULTS

The results are discussed hypothesis-wise as follows.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between Perceived Stress, Self-Efficacy and Academic Procrastination among college students.

Table 1:- Descriptive statistics and Correlation for Perceived Stress, Academic Procrastination, Self-Efficacy

	N	Mean	SD	1	2	3
Perceived Stress	70	24.14	4.531	-		
Academic Procrastination	70	94.87	8.131	.518**	-	
Self-Efficacy	70	32.51	2.908	-.325**	.518**	-

** p < 0.01

The collected data were scored, tabulated and their descriptive statistics were calculated.

The results were tested hypothesis and objective wise with inferential statistics.

SPSS.25. The obtained results are presented and discussed as follows.

Table 1 shows Mean and Standard Deviation of Perceived Stress, Academic Procrastination and Self-Efficacy. Mean score for Perceived stress is 24.14, for Academic Procrastination is 94.87 and for Self-Efficacy is 32.51. Standard Deviation for Perceived Stress is 4.531, for Academic Procrastination is 8.131 and Self-Efficacy is 2.908. The significance value is 0.006 which is less than 0.05 hence there is a correlation between self-efficacy and perceived stress. The significance value is 0.00 for academic procrastination and self-efficacy which is less than 0.05. This indicates the hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between Perceived Stress, Self-Efficacy and Academic Procrastination among college students is rejected. Further, however perceived stress and self-efficacy is negatively corelated.

H02: There is no significant influence of academic procrastination on Perceived Stress and Self-Efficacy among college students.

Table 2 Descriptive statistics and Regression for Perceived Stress and Self-Efficacy

Variable	B	β	SE
Constant	43.25		12.69
Perceived Stress	.298	.171	.215
Self-Efficacy	.366	.138	.326
R ²			.197
Δ R ²			.039

P > 0.05

Table 2 shows the descriptive statistics of regression. The B value and beta value of perceived stress .298 and .171 respectively. The b value and beta value for self-efficacy is .366 and .138 respectively.

The R² and adjusted R² values are .197 and .039, which means academic procrastination has only 3.9 % influence on self-efficacy and perceived stress. The significance value is .269, which is greater than 0.05. thus, the null hypothesis is accepted which states that there is no significant influence of academic procrastination on Perceived Stress and Self-Efficacy among college students.

IV. DISCUSSION

The study was done among college students pursuing under graduation and postgraduation in streams arts, commerce and science to assess the relationship between Perceived Stress, Self-Efficacy and Academic Procrastination among college students and to examine the influence of academic procrastination on Perceived Stress and Self-Efficacy among college students. The results showed that there is a significant relationship between Perceived Stress, Self-Efficacy and Academic Procrastination among college students and there is no significant influence of academic procrastination on Perceived Stress and Self-Efficacy among college students.

Academic procrastination can be an extremely serious issue for certain students, and the causes and functions of work postponement have received a lot of study attention in the recent decade. (Steel, 2007). Significant negative relationships with medium to high effect sizes were found between academic procrastination and three types of intrinsic academic motivation, one type of extrinsic academic motivation, and overall self-efficacy. (Cerino, 2014). (Ziegler & Opendakker, 2018) Academic procrastination is widely acknowledged as an affecting yet widespread occurrence in education. The interaction effects with time demonstrated a consistent procrastination-effort regulation link, although the association with metacognitive self-regulation and self-efficacy weakened over time. The findings support the notion of academic procrastination as a dynamic construct and emphasize the significance of early intervention. (Qian & Fuqiang, 2018) According to the study, academic procrastination mediates the impact of academic stress on academic performance. Individuals who feel academic stress will perform better if they actively procrastinate, whereas passive procrastination will result in bad performance. Furthermore, having a high sense of self-efficacy encourages active procrastination. (Zajacova et al., 2005) This study looks at the effects of academic self-efficacy and stress on the academic performance of 107 unconventional, mostly immigrant and minority college freshman at a big metropolitan commuting university. The findings imply that academic self-efficacy is a more reliable and consistent predictor of academic performance than stress. Previous research on the impact of academic self-efficacy on student academic performance has fascinated the interest of many researchers, particularly social scientists. Many studies have found that academic self-efficacy is strongly related to student academic performance.

Academic procrastination and academic self-efficacy may interact with other variables and ability levels. It is suggested that the study between them should be followed

by an experimental programme to measure academic procrastination and academic self-efficacy, offer counselling or project-based interventions, and then conduct a post-test to see if improvements were made. It would also be interesting to include as variables for future research teaching training, education, and attitudes towards students in developmental courses.

V. CONCLUSION

The following conclusion are drawn from the study:

There is a significant relationship between perceived stress, self-Efficacy and academic procrastination among college students.

There is no significant influence of academic procrastination on perceived stress and self-efficacy among college students.

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REFERENCES

- [1]. Alqudah, M., Alsubhien, A., & Al Heilat, M. (2014). The Relationship between the Academic Procrastination and Self-Efficacy among Sample of King Saud University Students. *Online*,5(16). <https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/document?repid=rep1&type=pdf&doi=e850a255cbcf59200c55c79f6c0af35908605971>
- [2]. Cerino, E. S. (2014). Relationships Between Academic Motivation, Self-Efficacy, and Academic Procrastination. *Psi Chi Journal of Psychological Research*, 19(4), 156–163. <https://doi.org/10.24839/2164-8204.jn19.4.156>
- [3]. Malkoç, A., & Mutlu, A. K. (2018). Academic Self-Efficacy and Academic Procrastination: Exploring the Mediating Role of Academic Motivation in Turkish University Students. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 6(10), 2087–2093. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1192728>
- [4]. Mehmet, K., Tahsin, İ., Ahmet, R. zpolat, & Mehmet, P. (2014). Analysis of academic self-efficacy, self-esteem and coping with stress skills predictive power on academic procrastination. *Educational Research and Reviews*, 9(5), 146–152. <https://doi.org/10.5897/err2014.1763>
- [5]. Qian, L., & Fuqiang, Z. (2018). ACADEMIC STRESS, ACADEMIC PROCRASTINATION AND ACADEMICPERFORMANCE: A MODERATED DUAL-MEDIATION MODEL. *Journal on Innovation and Sustainability. RISUS ISSN 2179-3565*, 9(2), 38. <https://doi.org/10.24212/2179-3565.2018v9i2p38-46>
- [6]. Zajacova, A., Lynch, S. M., & Espenshade, T. J. (2005). Self-Efficacy, Stress, and Academic Success in College. *Research in Higher Education*, 46(6), 677–706. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11162-004-4139-z>
- [7]. Ziegler, N., & Opdenakker, M.-C. (2018). The development of academic procrastination in first-year secondary education students: The link with metacognitive self-regulation, self-efficacy, and effort regulation. *Learning and Individual Differences*, 64, 71–82. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lindif.2018.04.009>